

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**COMBATING MUSCLE DAMAGE CAUSED BY WORKOUT
THROUGH NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL TECHNIQUES: A
NECESSARY EVIL**¹Dr. Muhammad Saad, ²Dr. Wasif Ali, ³Dr Waleed Khalid¹Punjab Medical College, Faisalabad, ²House Officer DHQ Teaching Hospital Gujranwala,
³MBBS, MO IYB DHQ Attock**Abstract:**

Incapacitating torment, firmness, delicacy, exhaustion, debilitated muscle work, the absence of solidarity resulting in practice are not invited by those not acclimated with it. It might dishearten a person from taking an interest in customary exercise. Various pharmacological and non-pharmacological systems have been utilized to lighten manifestations of muscle soreness, muscle torment, enhancing muscle work, the scope of movement and recuperation time. Non-steroidal calming drugs are recommended to beneficially affect muscle soreness, however, neglect to revive muscle shortcoming and scope of movement combined with muscle soreness. Besides, oral calming drugs are broadly used to moderate muscle soreness manifestations, yet ceaseless use can prompt distinctive symptoms as far as peptic ulcer and liver poisonous quality. Non-pharmacological cures and intercessions can be a superior decision. This account survey conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore (September 2017 to April 2018) is expected to give understanding into the non-pharmacological techniques to brush at exercise-incited muscle harm.

Keywords: *Eccentric Exercises, Muscle Soreness, Non-pharmacological Strategies, Unaccustomed Activity.*

Corresponding author:

Dr. Muhammad Saad,
Punjab Medical College, Faisalabad.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Saad et al., **Combating Muscle Damage Caused By Workout Through Non-Pharmacological Techniques: A Necessary Evil.**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2019; 06(02).

INTRODUCTION:

The underlying articulation on the crabbiness and aggravation of the muscle after the overwhelming physical movement was the first begat by Hough in 1902, who concocted a thought of the burst of the myofibre as a wellspring of activity actuated muscle harm (EIMD) prompting the deferred beginning of muscle soreness (DOMS) [1]. DOMS was recognized after quick and exceptional exercise, particularly unconventional or stretching withdrawal, as recommended by Asmussen and consequently settled by various scientists [2 – 4]. The myofibre harm was seen solely in the wake of protracting exercise [5]. In rodent type 1, myofibre was uncovered less powerless against strain than sort II fibres [6]. Similarly, in people, type II myofibre was uncovered increasingly defenceless against muscle harm following whimsical exercises [5]. There are differing speculations proposed about convincing EIMD: miniaturized scale injury, aggravation, lactic corrosive growth, electrolyte and compound convergence and muscle spasm [2]. Although these hypotheses have been portrayed independently from one another, the researchers have an accord that any individual hypothesis isn't adequate to depict the instrument; rather this capacity together. Provocative cells accumulation is arranged inside or out of the harmed myofibre following whimsical exercise, concentric activities and following stretching [7, 8].

DOMS INDUCTION:

Unaccustomed lively physical preparing prompts type I muscle strain damage confirm by muscle soreness [9], diminished muscle strength,3 constrained scope of movement (ROM), expanded muscle thickness [10], aching [4], solidness, tenderness [1] and diminished utilitarian movements [11]. These indications delivered by unpredictable activities are called DOMS. Ordinarily, it starts inside 12 hours of the novel or strenuous activity [12]. The pinnacle side effects show up in 2 – 3 days and it takes 5 – 7 days to disappears [2]. The force and span of preparing are the key variables to decide the seriousness of DOMS.

Specific preparing techniques have been embraced to deliver DOMS, including electrical stimulation [13], trail running [14], intentionally most extreme contraction [13], eccentric [3] concentric and extending exercises [8]. Interestingly, it is shown that there is less muscle harm in performing willful unpredictable activities contrasted with what is created by incitement even in isometrics [13]. Increased ROM and precise speed are straightforwardly identified with muscle harm while animating the nerve by surface anodes actuate no

harm [2].

BIOCHEMICAL FINDINGS:

Biochemical examinations of the prepared muscle have unveiled the development of lactic dehydrogenase and creatine kinase [15]. This uncovers myofibre damage is the wellspring of muscle soreness [16]. Previously, post-workout, the lactic corrosive collection was accepted one of the wellsprings of DOMS. Be that as it may, ongoing examinations on concentric activities ruin this hypothesis as concentric activities don't initiate soreness [5]. Normally, it takes one hour to come back to the pattern level after exercise. Therefore, it might be a wellspring of intense agony and solidness yet not a powerful particle amid pinnacle DOMS. Expanded resting solid movement and connective tissue damage have been accounted for as the wellspring of DOMS [7].

Following the unaccustomed movement, there is a disturbance of the sarcomere. Accordingly, there is a gradual addition of calcium, which causes more decay of the sarcomere. These intracellular demolition occasions lead to incendiary reactions and lift the cytokines and lymphocytes that inevitably improve agony recognition and soreness. Additionally, the nerve closure of the mechanoreceptor reacts to the development or control of potentiating soreness perception [17]. Non-pharmacological mediations to battle EIMD Prevention techniques are very little help as muscle soreness is an ordinary physiological reaction to energetic physical movement. There is an absence of critical logical information that avows or invalidates the value of accessible modalities. Nutraceuticals and other dietary sources [11, 18, 19], stretching [8], myofascial release [20], manual back rub therapy [21], mechanical pressure garments [22], physical agents [23], shunning unaccustomed strenuous physical exercises, physical and mental readiness, dynamic whimsical activities can diminish anticipated muscle soreness [17].

THE STRETCHING HOPE:

Stretching is believed to be a valuable cure, which regularly competitors perform to stay away from or constrict muscle soreness and to enhance muscle work. There is as yet an absence of huge proof in the case of extending has some job in weakening muscle soreness or boosting muscle execution. Ozmen et al in 2017 led an investigation to investigate the impact of dynamic, static extending and Kinesio taping on muscle soreness and adaptability following strenuous exercise. They included 65 youthful females and inspected the impact of this routine at 24 hours and

48 hours following the acceptance of muscle soreness in the hamstring. They presumed that these medications before strenuous activities may help in constricting muscle soreness, yet these have no job in enhancing muscle flexibility [8]. Interestingly, in another investigation, the scientists included 26 youthful, sound females and performed extending for about a month and demonstrated the surprising enhancement in hamstring flexibility [24]. Wang in 2017 played out an examination to break down the adequacy of both static and dynamic extending in 48 solid members in lower leg muscles and inferred that there was a period distinction in all factors. Be that as it may, the effect of extending was irrelevant on muscle soreness. It might be presumed that momentary extending practices potentially may have some gainful effect on muscle soreness, yet insignificantly affect muscle execution and flexibility [25]. Mild to direct force extending is prophylactically valuable in DOMS. Be that as it may, broad extending can be a wellspring of muscle harm.

THE MYOFASCIAL RELEASE HOPE:

Restoration specialists every now and again exhort myofascial discharge method by utilizing froth moving as a preventive or helpful solution for enhancing muscle recuperation, execution and ROM previously or after serious activities. Su Chang et al. led an investigation to watch the intense, preventive effect of froth moving, static and dynamic extending for adaptability, muscle quality, and muscle soreness. In a hybrid report plan, 15 male and 15 female youthful solid undergrads were enlisted. Isokinetic crest torque changed the Thomson test and sit and achieve test was presented. They presumed that froth roller is a better route than enhance adaptability without bringing down muscle strength [20]. Contrarily, a little portion of the shape roller did not create any huge difference [26]. Moderate and long-haul utilization of myofascial discharge (5 to 10 minutes/session) before initiating DOMS may have positive results as far as enhancing weariness and torment recognition.

THE NUTRICEUTICS HOPE:

Preventive or restorative utilization of dietary sources as cell reinforcements, nutrient D, protein and starch drinks are seen valuable. Information uncovered that protein and cancer prevention agents' enhancements can limit the impact of soreness and weakness partnered with strenuous activity [11, 18, 19].

Fish oil and nutrient D supplementation is proposed to have a huge effect to reduce muscle soreness. Tinsley et al. directed an examination to research the impact of fish oil on post-practice muscle soreness.

They reasoned that angle oil supplementation is extremely helpful to lighten post-practice muscle soreness [11] Ives et al. conducted an investigation to analyze the effect of protein and cancer prevention agent supplementation on muscle soreness, muscle capacity, and irritation. They had selected 60 inactive guys and evaluated isometric and isokinetic torque, muscle soreness and thigh boundary. They presumed that protein enhances muscle soreness and capacity. The expansion of cell reinforcement enhances more muscle work than utilizing protein and starch alone [18]. Curcumin or turmeric has calming and hostile to oxidant impacts and fits for damping muscle harm and rapid recuperation. In an ongoing report, analysts watched a huge enhancement in torment and muscle soreness after ingestion of oral curcumin. They had led an examination to look at the impact of curcumin in 17 men on muscle soreness and quality after concentrated offbeat exercise. They had taken oral curcumin (2.5 grams, two times per day) 2 days before the enlistment of muscle soreness. At 24 hours and 48 hours in the wake of actuating muscle soreness, they found a critical decrease of torment. Other than these impacts, curcumins likewise support muscle execution and calming markers [19]. The metabolic changes in EIMD drove the expanded interest for protein, particularly in games including strenuous physical exercises. Nutraceuticals can be helpful in mitigating the side effects and boosting rapid recuperation.

THE MESSAGE HOPE:

Backrub is proposed to potently affect mitigating DOMS side effects. In any case, the outcomes from logical examinations on back rub are equivocal [21, 27, 29]. These varieties in results might be associated with the application strategies, planning and term of back rub application. Moreover, the instrument of activity is as yet equivocal. Backrub treatment is a valuable cure, and patients regularly trust rub for DOMS agony and soreness help, or to turn away different manifestations. At present, minimal logical information is accessible focused on the viability of back rub on muscle soreness and torment following strenuous exercise. Moreover, the viability of a back rub in DOMS is questionable. Almost no information is accessible which bolsters the adequacy of back rubs as a solution for constricting muscle soreness and torment. Torres et al. inspected the viability of back rub by breaking down [9] thinks about on back rub and found a slight enhancement in symptoms [27] Guo et al. led a logical investigation on the adequacy of back rub following DOMS and recommended that it very well may be a promising solution for enhancing muscle work and constricting DOMS indications. They included 11 articles in the

wake of satisfying the incorporation criteria and found that knead altogether diminishes the soreness rating and muscle work. Additionally, creatine phosphokinase (CPK) level was likewise brought down in subjects taking back rub treatment. Almost certainly, it is extraordinary news for managing DOMS with massage [21]. On the other hand, Imtiaz et al, in 2014 found that rub has an insignificant job in reestablishing DOMS torment contrasted with vibration treatment. They discovered vibration treatment increasingly helpful in bringing down lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) level and limiting muscle pain [29]. Similarly, an audit recognized back rub treatment a less encouraging VS calming. Zainuddin et al. in 2005 demonstrated that rub has a measurably critical effect on easing torment connected with DOMS, yet neglected to demonstrate the effect of back rub on muscle shortcoming and function [28]. Massage can lessen aggravation connected to muscle harm. How to knead functions, still remains a puzzle. The use of back rub can't have institutionalized and it is emotional, so its adequacy relies upon conditions and the aptitude dimension of the specific specialist.

THE MECHANICAL COMPRESSION HOPE:

Mechanical pressure as pressure articles of clothing is being utilized regularly in venous hemodynamics. As of late, mechanical pressure has been proposed for the alleviation of muscle soreness by diminishing the irritation, torment and encouraging speedy recuperation after unaccustomed exercise [30]. Evidence for lessening DOMS and EIMD indications are clashing, both confirming and invalidating the viability of pressure garments [14, 22]. An investigation has shown that consistent mechanical pressure upheld the protection of muscle quality, muscle soreness, muscle execution and ROM [22]. Hill et al. in 2017 researched the impact of pressure pieces of clothing in lightening the indications related to EIMS and DOMS. They had taken 45 recreational, dynamic members and inferred that weight applies a huge impact on muscle recuperation after unaccustomed exercise [22]. Continues pressure treatment can confine the seriousness of the indications related to DOMS.

THE PHYSICAL AGENTS HOPE:

Physical specialists like warmth and cool treatment are utilized broadly to adapt to post-practice muscle torment, weakness and muscle soreness for centuries [9, 31]. Cold treatment is ordinarily used to mitigate muscle soreness. In any case, as of late analysts recommended that warm treatment has a decent prophylactic impact on enhancing muscle adaptability, muscle soreness and muscle

performance [9]. Most researchers have an agreement that chilly treatment is the better restorative intercession than manage intense tissue harm, muscle soreness and irritation basically identified with games injuries [31, 32]. The cooling treatment in games medication has been recognized as a crucial cure. As of late, it was shown that the chilly water drenching is a viable creates to disparage torment, aggravation, and weakness ensuing to thorough exercise [32]. Whole-body cooling is another protected and potential technique to adapt to abuse disorder, muscle wounds and to cut the fixed time between the preparation time frames. This treatment neglects to bring on any changes in haematological and biochemical parameters. It was assumed that entire body cooling is protected contrasted with the ice bag and does not cause any harming effect on athletes [33, 34]. Pre-preparing warm-up or warm treatment and post-preparing cryotherapy as entire body cooling is suggestive to stay away from muscle soreness.

ECCENTRIC EXERCISE HOPE:

Customized practices are one of the valuable solutions for constricting muscle agony, soreness, and execution after EIMD pursued by unaccustomed activities. Constant exercise is a standout amongst the most valuable instruments to battle muscle soreness. The arrival of endorphins, which decreases agony and enhancement in neighbourhood blood course following activity might be the contributing variable in alleviating muscle soreness symptoms [17]. Furthermore, erratic exercise evokes various wellbeing advancing advantages as enhanced insulin affectability, oxidative pressure and provocative status [7]. Initially, offbeat activities have an expert incendiary reaction, however, later on, they initiate a mitigating response [35]. Sports person ought to be prepared to cut down the activity span and power for 24 to 48 hours following EIMD or play out an activity on the unaffected body parts [8]. Moderate load activities ought to be urged to perform continuously more than 1-2 weeks so as to abstain from preparing interruption or muscle harm.

CONCLUSION:

Nutriceuticals, physician specialists, myofascial discharge and moderate power ordinary activities are prescribed to battle DOMS and its side effects. Pre-preparing extending or warmth and post-preparing myofascial discharge and cool treatment can be contrived to restrict the side effects of DOMS. The survey speaks to only one segment of a basic leadership process. Cautious checking of the side effects emerging from muscle damage requires finding and the executives by a clinician. Future

examinations are prescribed to locate the prophylactic impact of present moment myofascial discharge on DOMS.

REFERENCES:

- Zainuddin Z, Newton M, Sacco P, Nosaka K. Effects of massage on delayed-onset muscle soreness, swelling, and recovery of muscle function. *J Athl Train.* 2005; 40: 174-80.
- Imtiyaz S, Veqar Z, Shareef MY. To Compare the Effect of Vibration Therapy and Massage in Prevention of Delayed Onset Muscle Soreness (DOMS). *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2014; 8:133 - 6.
- Hill J, Howatson G, van Someren K, Leeder J, Pedlar C. Compression garments and recovery from exercise-induced muscle damage: a meta-analysis. *Br J Sports Med.* 2014; 48: 1340-6.
- Hohenauer E, Taeymans J, Baeyens JP, Clarys P, Clijnen R. The Effect of Post-Exercise Cryotherapy on Recovery Characteristics: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *PLoS One.* 2015; 10: e0139028.
- Abadia AE, Lamblin J, Delacroix B, Leduc C, McCall A, Nedelec M, et al. Recovery from Exercise-Induced Muscle Damage: Cold-Water Immersion Versus Whole-Body Cryotherapy. *Int J Sports Physiol Perform.* 2017; 12: 402-9.
- Takagi R, Fujita N, Arakawa T, Kawada S, Ishii N, Miki A. Influence of icing on muscle regeneration after crush injury to skeletal muscles in rats. *J Appl Physiol (1985).* 2011; 110: 382-8.
- Banfi G, Lombardi G, Colombini A, Melegati G. Whole-body cryotherapy in athletes. *Sports Med.* 2010; 40: 509-17.
- Paulsen G, Mikkelsen UR, Raastad T, Peake JM. Leucocytes, cytokines and satellite cells: what role do they play in muscle damage and regeneration following eccentric exercise. *Exerc Immunol Rev.* 2012; 18: 42-97.
- Qaisar R, Bhaskaran S, Van Remmen H. Muscle fibre type diversification during exercise and regeneration. *Free Radic Biol Med.* 2016; 98: 56-67.
- Margarites NV, Theodorou AA, Baltzopoulos V, Maganaris CN, Paschalis V, Kyparos A, et al. Muscle damage and inflammation after eccentric exercise: can the repeated bout effect be removed? *Physiol Rep.* 2015; 3: e12648.
- Ozmen T, Yagmur Gunes G, Dogan H, Ucar I, Willems M. The effect of Kinesio taping versus stretching techniques on muscle soreness, and flexibility during recovery from Nordic hamstring exercise. *J Body Mov Ther.* 2017; 21: 41-7.
- Petrofsky J, Berk L, Bains G, Khowailed IA, Lee H, Laymon M. The Efficacy of Sustained Heat Treatment on Delayed-Onset Muscle Soreness. *Clin J Sports Med.* 2017; 27: 329-37.
- Lee YS, Bae SH, Hwang JA, Kim KY. The effects of Kinesio taping on architecture, strength and pain of muscles in delayed onset muscle soreness of biceps brachii. *J Phys Ther Sci.* 2015; 27: 457-9.
- Tinsley GM, Gann JJ, Huber SR, Andre TL, La Bounty PM, Bowden RG, et al. Effects of fish oil supplementation on post resistance exercise muscle soreness. *J diet support.* 2017; 14: 89-100.
- Prasartwuth O, Taylor JL, Gandevia SC. Maximal force, voluntary activation and muscle soreness after eccentric damage to human elbow flexor muscles. *J Physiol.* 2005; 567:337-48.
- Cramer RM, Aagaard P, Qvortrup K, Langberg H, Olesen J, Kjaer M. Myofibre damage in human skeletal muscle: effects of electrical stimulation versus voluntary contraction. *J Physiol.* 2007; 583: 365- 80.
- Kerhervé HA, Samozino P, Descombe F, Pinay M, Millet GY, Pasqualini M, et al. Calf Compression Sleeves Change Biomechanics but Not Performance and Physiological Responses in Trail Running. *Front Physiol.* 2017; 8:247.
- Ra SG, Miyazaki T, Kojima R, Komine S, Ishikura K, Kawanaka K, et al. Effect of BCAA supplement timing on exercise-induced muscle soreness and damage: a pilot placebo-controlled double-blind study. *J Sports Med Phys Fitness.* 2017.
- Mirzayev JA. Muscle damage: Scientific fundamentals. *J Appl Physiol (1985).* 2017; 122: 1052.
- Cheung K, Hume P, Maxwell L. Delayed onset muscle soreness: treatment strategies and performance factors. *Sports Med.* 2003; 33: 145-64.
- Ives SJ, Bloom S, Matias A, Morrow N, Martins N, Roh Y, et al. Effects of a combined protein and antioxidant supplement on the recovery of muscle function and soreness following eccentric exercise. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr.* 2017; 14: 21.
- Nicol LM, Rowlands DS, Fazakerly R, Kelllett J. Curcumin supplementation likely attenuates delayed onset muscle soreness (DOMS). *Eur J Appl Physiol.* 2015; 115: 1769-77.
- Su H, Chang NJ, Wu WL, Guo LY, Chu IH. Acute Effects of Foam Rolling, Static Stretching, and Dynamic Stretching During Warm-Ups on Muscular Flexibility and Strength in Young Adults. *J Sports Rehabil.* 2017; 26:469-77.
- Guo J, Li L, Gong Y, Zhu R, Xu J, Zou J, et al. Massage Alleviates Delayed Onset Muscle

- Soreness after Strenuous Exercise: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Front Physiol.* 2017; 8: 747.
25. Hill J, Howatson G, van Someren K, Gaze D, Legg H, Lineham J, et al. Effects of Compression Garment Pressure on Recovery from Strenuous Exercise. *Int J Sports Physiol Perform.* 2017; 12:1078-84.
 26. Meline T, Watier T, Sanchez AM. Cold water immersion after exercise: recent data and perspectives on "aromatherapy". *J Physiol.* 2017; 595: 2783-4.
 27. Manjari P, Jones DA, Mickevicius M, Satkunskiene D, Snieckus A, Rutkauskaite R, et al. The effects of 4 weeks stretching training to the point of pain on flexibility and muscle-tendon unit properties. *Eur J Appl Physiol.* 2017; 117: 1713-25.
 28. Wang Y. The Efficacy of Dynamic Contract-Relax Stretching on Delayed-Onset Muscle Soreness Among Healthy Individuals: *Clin J Sports Med.* 2018; 28:28-36.
 29. Murray AM, Jones TW, Horobeanu C, Turner AP, Sproule J. Sixty seconds of foam rolling does not affect functional flexibility or change muscle temperature in adolescent athletes. *Int J Sports Phys Ther.* 2016; 11:765-76.
 30. Torres R, Ribeiro F, Duarte JA, Cabri JM. Evidence of the physiotherapeutic interventions used currently after exercise-induced muscle damage: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Phys Ther Sport.* 2012; 13:101-14.
 31. Kruszyniewicz J, Skoniecznaydecka K, Sroka R, Adler G. The analgesic efficacy of Kinesiology taping in delayed onset muscle soreness (DOMS). *Central Euro J Sports Sci Med.* 2016; 1: 73-9.
 32. Mizumura K, Taguchi T. Delayed onset muscle soreness: Involvement of neurotrophic factors. *J Physiol Sci.* 2016; 66: 43-52.
 33. Haksever B, Kinikli GI, Tunay VB, Karahan S, Donmez G. Effect of kinesiotope intervention on knee muscle strength and delayed onset muscle soreness pain following eccentric fatigue training. *Turk J physiother Rehabil-fizyoterapi Rehabil.* 2016; 27: 12-8.
 34. Lindahl AK. The effect of intermittent pneumatic compression on the management of pain associated with delayed onset muscle soreness, 2016.
 35. Douglas J, Pearson S, Ross A, McGuigan M. Eccentric Exercise: Physiological Characteristics and Acute Responses. *Sports Med.* 2017; 47: 663-75.